

-3 As the created root of all mathematics by numbers, Prime number 5 as the created template of all Prime number and pseudo-prime numbers(Mathematical Proof)

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Abstract: The author has published several papers with JPRM which were unorthodox, but these have led to the acceptance of a major book on created mathematics, this small paper validates JPRM, and is a challenge to the entire current numbers theory if understood correctly. This small paper is the basic proof of the base of numbers in the created mathematics of the -1 cone of Pythagoras 1:3 as Published at JPRM (see reference), with the double spiral arrangement of the Prime numbers and their multiples by the template of prime number 5, as the basis. This is shown separately in an upcoming book on created mathematics. The table entered in this paper is the precise cardinal proof of numbers, to validate the premise of created mathematics at Pythagoras 1:3 and to refute current numbers theory.

Key words: -3, prime number 5.

Description:

The natural root of mathematical numbers is -3 as shown clearly in the table below, and that the value of prime number 5 in the created mathematics is the exclusive constant template for all Prime numbers and Pseudo-prime numbers at a rhythm of +10,+20 as 10:20:10:20:10:20..... This is clearly established by the description of the two mathematics series, A and B, as follows.

Series A. These prime numbers and pseudo -prime numbers as naturally arranged at the half-line of the 1:3 cone(Series A).

Series B is derived from natural tri-sets of the natural numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9 at +5, by exactly the same rhythm of 10:20:10:20, as for series A.

There is a fixed relationship between the two natural series A and B of Prime numbers and Pseudo prime numbers that is mathematically and geometrically predictive by sieve of all prime number placements shown separately in the upcoming book and alluded to in the published paper as minor caveat.

+4	7	10	13	16	19	22	25	28	31	34	37	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61
+3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60

This above numbers arrangement at the half-line is indefinitely progressive , briefly there is this arrangement of the double spirals , an outer spiral and a replicated inner spiral

Outer Spiral in spiral placement, multiples of 5 at 10:20:10:20:10:20, this is *infinite*

5(1)		25(5)		55(11)		85(17)		115(23)	
	10(2)		35(7)		65(13)		95(19)		125(25)

Inner spiral (precise replicate of outer spiral)

5		11		17		23		29	
	7		13		19		25		31

Continuation:

outer	spiral								
145(29)		175(35)		205(41)		235(47)		265(53)	
	155(31)		185(37)		215(43)		245(49)		
inner	spiral								
35		41		47		53		59	
	37		43		49		55		

Series B

(The natural prime number +5 and the basis for numbers placement derived from the tri-sets of the natural numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10.....)

-3is the abstract created root of all mathematics by numbers, Prime number 5 as the created template of all Prime number and pseudo-prime numbers (Mathematical Proof). -1:-3 is an abstract deduction and cannot form a point in any Geometry, but its existence is confirmed here.

This clear table of the weave of mathematics at the natural tri-sets of this numbers series B starting at the base of numbers, clearly proves and demonstrates the fact that Prime number 5 is the predictable template of 10:20:10:20:10 for all *prime numbers and pseudo- prime numbers*, concurrently in both these series . Please focus in the *left column* and the *right column* and clearly on your own understand the predictability of prime number 5 at +5 by numbers in the left column and by +10, +20, +30 +40+50 in that ascending order in increments of the value 10 in the right column . Note that starting at base numbers of mathematics that the red numbers are comprised solely of Prime numbers, and their multiples (Pseudo prime numbers) in sequence . Clearly the root value of the tri-sets of natural numbers placement is abstract -3(-3+5=2) as in the table below

Table by Tri-sets of created numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8----- extreme left column are the numbers at +5, and I the extreme right column is the value at all +10 , as divided by 5 it is obvious is a constant +10, it is also obvious that the negative root is -3(abstract)

1	2	3		3*1	=	2	+1	/5						
2*	3	4		4*2	=	3	+5	1		1	-	2	=	-1
3	4	5		5*3	=	4	+11							
4	5	6		6*4	=	5	+19							
5	6	7		7*5	=	6	+29							
6	7	8		8*6	=	7	+41							
7*	8	9		9*7	=	8	+55	11		11	-	1	=	10
8	9	10		10*8	=	9	+71							
9	10	11		11*9	=	10	+89							
10	11	12		12*10	=	11	+109							
11	12	13		13*11	=	12	+131							
12*	13	14		14*12	=	13	+155	31		31	-	11	=	20
13	14	15		15*13	=	14	+181							
14	15	16		16*14	=	15	+209							
15	16	17		17*15	=	16	+239							
16	17	18		18*16	=	17	+271							
17*	18	19		19*17	=	18	+305	61		61	-	31	=	30
18	19	20		20*18	=	19	+341							
19	20	21		21*19	=	20	+379							
...
22*	23	24		24*20	=	23	+505	101		101	-	61	=	40
27*	28	29		29*27	=	28	+755	151		151	-	101	=	50
32*	33	34		34*32	=	33	+1055	211		211	-	151	=	60
37*	38	39		39*37	=	38	+1405	281		281	-	211	=	70
42*	43	44		44*42	=	43	+1805	361		361	-	281	=	80
47*	48	49		49*47	=	48	+2255	451		451	-	361	=	90
52*	53	54		54*52	=	53	+2755	551		551	-	441	=	100
57*	58	59		59*57	=	58	+3305	661		661	-	551	=	110
62*	63	64		64*62	=	63	+3905	781		781	-	661	=	120
67*	68	69		69*67	=	68	+4555	911		911	-	781	=	130
72*	73	74		74*72	=	73	+5255	1051		1051	-	911	=	140
77*	78	79		79*77	=	78	+6005	1201		1201	-	1051	=	150

And, as a further example for the numbers 1-19 from the table above table the gaps are 4,6,8,10,12,14,16.....(5-1=4;11-5=6;19-11=8.....)

And, from the table above also the following deduction:

$$379-341=38(19*2)$$

$$341-305=36(18*2)$$

$$305-271=34(17*2)$$

$$271-239=32(16*2)$$

239-209=30(15*2)
 209-181=28(14*2)
 181-155=26(13*2)
 155-131=24(12*2)
 131-109=22(11*2)
 109-89=20(10*2)
 89-71=18(9*2)
 71-55=16(8*2)
 55-41=14(7*2)

41-29=12(6*2)
 29-19=10(5*2)
 19-11=8(4*2)
 11-5=6(3*2)
 5-1=4 (2*2)

As these numbers in this precise series B as shown above by the tables as +5, are further segregated by prime numbers and pseudo-prime numbers, we clearly get the following fixed series with the Prime numbers/pseudo-prime numbers (in bold) arranged clearly in the template rhythm of 10:20:10:20:10

Minus -3= (-3+5=2)

3,2,7,12,17,22,27,32,37,42,47,52,57,62,67,72,77,82,87,92,97,102,107,112,117,122,127,132,137
 segregated as: **7:17:37:47:67:77:97:107,127,137**.....(10:20:10:20:10...by gaps),

Series A and B above are parallel series in mathematical ligand.

Based on this above, this following is further proof that the arrangement of the *basic constant* of the template of Prime 5 with all prime numbers and their multiples and Regular numbers (10:20:10: 20:10:20...) is exactly the same rhythm in both series A and B, proving the fact that the arrangement at 1:3 is parallel to regular numbers tri-sets at +5, This is a proof of the constant template of Prime number 5 . Further proof is by the text in the book to be published

The two series of prime numbers/pseudo prime numbers derived by the 10:20:10:20 rhythm are as follows .

The plus values are rationally predictable and parallel at both the series A and B, at gaps of 12 :24:12:24:12:24 as an indefinite series.

B:7	17	37	47	67	77	97	107	127	137	157	167		187	197	217
A:5	7	11	13	17	19	23	25	29	31	35	37		41	43	47
(A+B)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+
12	24	48	60	84	96	120	132	156	168	192	204		228	240	264
(A-B)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	-	-
2	10	26	34	50	58	74	82	98	106	122	130		146	154	170
(1)	(5)	(13)	(17)	(25)	(29)	(37)	(41)	(49)	(53)	(61)	(65)		(73)	(77)	(85)

The *minus-* values above are also constant at gaps of 8:16: 8:16:8:16 :8 as (2,10,26,34,50,58,74,82,98,106,122,130,146,154,,170,,,...).Interestingly these latter minus values divided by 2 are the exact replicate of the inner spiral values and are comprised exclusively of prime numbers and pseudoprime number with ordinated skipping of the prime numbers and pseudo -prime numbers in ordinate i.e. 2,5 (7,11),13,17(19,23),25,29 (31,35), 37, 41(43,47), 49,53(55,59), 61, 65, (67,71) ,73, 77, (79,83), 85.

All the double spiral arrangement of prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers at the half-line of the 1:3 cone is directly dictated by the rhythm of prime number 5(10:20:10:20:20,..) as follows, outer spiral(OS) and inner spiral (IS), its replicate(5), in the table below

OS	5	25	35	55	65	85	95	115	125	145	155	175	185	205
IS	1	5	7	11	13	17	19	23	25	29	31	35	37	41
OS	215	235	245	265	275	295	305	325	335	355	365	385	395	415
IS	43	47	49	53	55	59	61	65	67	71	73	77	79	83

Conclusion:

In the final analysis the correct number arrangement is in a double spiral at the cone progression of Pythagoras 1:3 which arrangement as shown in series A, is parallel with series B derived from the tri-sets of the natural arrangement of numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9..... This method has led to further sieve of the double spiral to isolate prime numbers, that method is shown by a separate book and is detailed also in an upcoming book.

References:

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